

Indian Rockphosphates for Direct Application to the Soil

DASHRATH SINGH¹ and N. P. DATTA²

Division of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi

Manuscript received 23 December 1972; accepted 7 May 1973

The phosphorus fertilizer value of Laccadive and Mussoorie phosphates for direct application was compared with the Gafsa phosphate in a green house experiment. Indian rock phosphates inspite of low analysis with respect to Phosphorus compare fairly well with imported Gafsa rock phosphate when evaluated on the basis of dry matter yield and phosphorus content of pea crop.

INDIA'S phosphate fertilizer industry is based on imported raw materials in view of the unsuitability of indigenous phosphate rocks for such processing. Ground rockphosphates are known to substitute the other commercial phosphatic fertilizers in acid soils. Rockphosphates have been used for direct application to the soil with varying degrees of success and large quantities are being consumed in U.S.A. and U.S.S.R. In India where the phosphatic fertilizers are in short supply and large quantities of rockphosphates have been discovered in the country, an attempt for evaluation of rockphosphates for direct application to the soil have been made in the present investigation.

Experimental

Surface soil samples representing Palampur (*pH* 4.9), Dinhatra (*pH* 5.5) and Delhi (*pH* 6.8) (Physico-chemical characteristics given in Table 1) were mixed with rockphosphates at 160 kg P_2O_5 per hectare level. Rockphosphate samples from Mussoorie (U.P. State), Laccadive (Laccadive islands) and Gafsa (Africa) were ground to pass through 200 mesh sieve (Chemical characteristics given in Table 2). Nitrogen and potash at 200 kg per hectare level were added as basal dressing. Well decomposed farm yard manure at the rate of 120 quintals per hectare was used as the source of organic matter. The fertilizers were

Total phosphorus in soils and fertilizers was estimated from the sodium carbonate fusion extract². Soils for sesquioxides and phosphaterocks for citrate soluble phosphorus were analysed with official methods¹. Iron estimations were carried out with dichromate titration³. Cation exchange capacity determination of soils was carried out with Schollenbarger's procedure⁷. Available phosphorus in soils was determined by Bray procedure³.

TABLE 2. ANALYSIS OF PHOSPHATE ROCKS

Phosphate source	Content of phosphoric acid (P_2O_5)	
	Total %	Soluble in ammonium citrate (% of total)
Mussoorie rock phosphate	23.1	13.0
Laccadive phosphate earth	12.5	30.8
Gafsa rock phosphate	36.0	26.1

Results and Discussion

Results of dry matter yield of pea crop are presented in Table 3. In Kangra soil (*pH* 4.9) all the phosphate rocks involved in the present investigations were of

TABLE 1. PHYSICO-CHEMICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF SOILS

Soil	Total phosphorus (% P_2O_5)	Crude sesquioxides (% R_2O_3)	Total iron (% F_2O_3)	C.E.C. (me/100 g)	Available phosphorus (P_2O_5 Kg/ha)
Kangra	0.08	25.66	5.33	16.20	12.00
Dinhata	0.17	23.35	3.00	14.00	10.00
Delhi	0.06	16.66	2.00	10.20	8.00

mixed with the soil contained in earthen pots coated with bituminous black paint from inside.

1. Assistant Soil Scientist, Indian Grassland and Fodder Research Institute, Jhansi (U.P.).
2. Project Director, Nuclear Research Laboratory, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi.

equal fertilizer value in supplying phosphate to pea crop as evidenced by dry matter yields. Addition of farm yard manure along with the phosphate rocks increased crop yields in all except Gafsa rock phosphate. The acidity produced from farm yard manure decomposition was probably insufficient to break the apatite structure of Gafsa rock phosphate.

TABLE 3. DRY MATTER YIELD OF PEA CROP AS AFFECTED BY PHOSPHATE SOURCES

Treatments (P ₂ O ₅ applied @ 160 kg/ha)	Mean yield (Average of three replications) 8 per plot		
	Kangra	Dinhata	Delhi
Laccadive phosphate earth	9.50	21.18	9.07
Laccadive phosphate earth + FYM	18.43	20.16	14.20
Mussoorie rock phosphate	5.80	19.71	6.78
Mussoorie rock phosphate + FYM	10.71	38.20	7.66
Gafsa rock phosphate	8.71	30.40	8.00
Gafsa rock phosphate + FYM	8.86	30.40	9.70
FYM only (control)	2.95	15.40	3.11
Nitrogen and potash (control)	3.00	16.40	8.90
C.D. 5%	4.07	16.61	4.60

Phosphate composition of the crop showed trend similar to dry matter yield of pea. There was no significant difference between the phosphate sources involved in the present investigations as evidenced by dry matter yield and phosphate composition of pea crop.

TABLE 4. PHOSPHATE COMPOSITION OF PEA CROP (%P₂O₅) UNDER PHOSPHATE ROCK TREATMENTS

Treatments (P ₂ O ₅ applied @ 160 kg/ha)	Mean phosphate composition (Average of three replications)		
	Kangra	Dinhata	Delhi
Laccadive phosphate earth	0.058	0.106	0.049
Laccadive phosphate earth + FYM	0.043	0.174	0.029
Mussoorie rock phosphate	0.087	0.031	0.047
Mussoorie rock phosphate + FYM	0.050	0.036	0.037
Gafsa rock phosphate	0.055	0.026	0.031
Gafsa rock phosphate + FYM	0.053	0.041	0.031
FYM only (control)	0.014	0.018	0.023
Nitrogen and potash (control)	0.015	0.014	0.022
C.D. 5%	0.005	0.096	0.005

In another acid soil from Dihata (pH 5.5) there was no significant affect of phosphate application on dry matter yield of crop and also no significant differences were observed between the various phosphate sources. This was because of high phosphate fertility of this soil. Addition of farm yard manure along with the phosphate rocks did not prove to be of any help in improving the dry matter yields. Phosphate composition figures were also not significant over those of control. Because of the soil being rich in phosphorus and relatively higher soil pH rock phosphates have not proved to be promising in Dinhata soil when adjudged from crop yield and phosphate composition.

In a near neutral soil from Delhi (pH 6.8) which was poor in phosphate fertility rock phosphate addition increased crop yields significantly over no phosphate treatments. The beneficial effect of farm yard manure additions with rock phosphate has been observed only in the case of Laccadive phosphate earths because of being low analysis material. Phosphate composition of the crop in Delhi soil amongst various treatments also did differ significantly.

For direct application of rock phosphates to the soil the soil fertility with respect to phosphorus is an important criterion. Rock phosphates can be used as a substitute to commercial phosphatic fertilizers on soils low in available phosphorus. Farm yard manure when applied along with the phosphate rocks increased the solubility of phosphorus contained in these materials which support the contention of 4, 5, 6, 8.

References

1. A.O.A.C. Official Methods of Analysis, 7th Ed., Washington D.C., 1950.
2. F. E. BEAR, Chemistry of the Soil 2nd Ed., American Chemical Society Monograph Series No. 160, 1965.
3. R. H. BRAY and L. T. KURTZ, *Soil Sci.*, 1945, 59, 39.
4. C. H. CHOU and T. C. LEU, *Acta. Pedol. Scin.*, 1957, 5, 215.
5. V. K. LEMPTESKALFA, *Mest. Mineral Udobr. Ukrain. SSR*, 1954, 1, 121.
6. L. F. SEATZ, A. J. STEGER and J. C. KRAMER, *Proc. Soil Sci. Soc. Amer.*, 1959, 23, 374.
7. C. J. SCHOLLENBERGER, *Soil Sci.*, 1930, 30, 161.
8. K. SIK and T. NIZASALOVSKY, *Orsz. Mezőgazd. Minőség-irt. Rvk.*, 1961, 5, 297.
9. A. I. VOGEL, A text book of quantitative inorganic analysis. 3rd Ed., Longmans Green & Co., London, 1962.